

ACTS OF RECOGNITION AND LEARNER'S IDENTITY

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Abstract

In recent decades, students have perceived that what they learn at school lacks meaning, as it does not align with their interests, objectives, and projects (Coll, 2013). An effective way to address this problem is to help students develop a favorable Learner's Identity (LI).

LI is the set of meanings that people construct about themselves as learners with certain characteristics and capacities to learn. The LI conditions the development opportunities that each experience entails. When students develop a favorable LI they can face new challenges and learning situations in a wide variety of contexts and reach achievement experiences that reinforce their learning competencies and enable the attribution of meaning to what they learn (Falsafi & Coll, 2015).

The LI is partly built from the Acts of Recognition (AoR) that significant people such as teachers offer to students. AoR are explicit or implicit actions aimed at providing students with information about their characteristics as learners. When students recognize and internalize these AoR as a Sense of Recognition (SoR) of their ability to learn, their LI can be positively impacted (Falsafi & Coll, 2015; Saballa, 2019).

This research project aims to study a teacher's AoR with the greatest potential to generate SoR and positively impact students' LI, improving their perception of competence and their ability to attribute meaning to what they learn at school.

We developed a case study of qualitative methodology in a primary Tutoring practice at a Chilean school. This school organizes its teaching based on *personal learning plans* that are built upon the strengths, needs, and interests of each student. Each Tutoring cycle lasts one week and is organized into three daily sessions: *check-in*, *follow-up*, and *check-out*. During one week we carried out 14 classroom observations, which were video-recorded and complemented with a written record. We conducted two interviews with the participating teacher to understand the design and development of the practice and its assessment.

Our object of analysis was the teacher's AoR with the greatest potential to impact students' LI. As an operational criterion, we took as AoR any teaching action that provided students, individually or collectively, with positive or negative information about themselves as persons and/or learners. For the content analysis, we constructed four categories of AoR based on the aspects of students that were recognized: (1) their characteristics as learners, (2) their belonging and/or contribution within the learning community, (3) their protagonist role in the teaching and learning processes, and (4) their value as individual persons, beyond their role as learners.

Table 1 shows that the different categories of AoR were mostly concentrated in the *check-in* and *check-out* sessions, especially in sessions 3 and 10 (13 and 14 AoR), and to a lesser extent in the *follow-up* sessions (1 AoR in sessions 11 and 14).

Table 1: AoR distributed by session

Day	1			2			3			4			5		Total
Session	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	
AoR															
(1) Characteristics as learners	2	1	0	0	4	4	2	3	4	6	0	2	2	0	30
(2) Belonging to community	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	3
(3) Protagonist role	2	2	6	1	3	3	3	1	4	3	1	1	0	1	31
(4) Value as persons	3	1	6	1	1	1	4	2	3	5	0	5	7	0	39
Total	7	4	13	3	8	8	9	6	10	14	1	9	9	1	103

The most frequent AoR of the teacher (see Table 1) were those that recognized students beyond their role as learners, mainly embodied in friendly manners, demonstrations of concern for their feelings and personal affairs, emotional attunement, and occasional reinforcement of their socio-emotional characteristics (37.8%). These were followed by AoR of their characteristics as learners and/or abilities to address learning activities (30%). With a similar incidence, the teacher offered actions that sought to give students a protagonist role in their learning processes, by allowing them to make some decisions about them (29.1%). Lastly, and to a much lesser extent (2.9%), she recognized students as a part and/or contribution to the learning community, by seeking the participation of all in classroom activities.

We can conclude from the data that the observations and categories were effective instruments for our objective since they allowed us to identify a large number and variety of AoR performed by the teacher. Also, that the recognition of the *person* behind the learner was the most frequent type of AoR. Although these acts did not directly recognize their characteristics as learners, they may have been intended to create a climate of trust and/or a teacher-student bond that reinforces the internalization of AoR and their impact on LI (Campos et al. 2015; Saballa, 2019).

To verify this thesis, it is necessary to carry out new research focused on in-depth interviews with students to understand their interpretation of AoR and their impact on LI and meaning.

Keywords: acts of recognition, attribution of meaning, learner's identity, sense of recognition

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